

Reed Solomon Coded M -ary Hyper Phase-Shift Keying

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Abstract – Non-binary forward error correction (FEC) coding in conjunction with M -ary hyper phase-shift keying (MHPSK) is considered in order to improve the robustness of a satellite communications uplink. MHPSK is a spectrally efficient modulation technique that uses four orthonormal basis functions to increase the distance between different symbols in the signal space. Spectral efficiency and probability of bit error are two key figures of merit used to evaluate digital modulation techniques. The use of four orthonormal basis functions provides an advantage over traditional modulation techniques such as M -ary phase-shift keying (MPSK) and M -ary quadrature amplitude keying (MQAM) that only possess two degrees of freedom. MHPSK offers an improvement in bit error performance over other spectrally efficient modulation techniques for the same average energy per bit-to-noise power spectral density ratio and similar spectral efficiency. As a result, MHPSK offers a novel way to improve both throughput and reduce power requirements using easy to generate waveforms. In this paper, Reed Solomon coded symbols are assumed to be transmitted with MHPSK. MHPSK, MPSK, and MQAM are compared in terms of probability of bit error and bandwidth efficiency, where the number of bits per coded symbol are typically designed to match the number of bits per channel symbol.

Index Terms – spectral efficiency, orthonormal, phase shift-keying, probability of bit error, forward error correction.

I. INTRODUCTION

M -ary hyper phase-shift keying (MHPSK) modulation is a novel equal energy per symbol modulation technique that utilizes four-dimensions to increase the minimum Euclidean distance between symbol constellation points. The literature contains several references to modulation techniques that utilize multi-dimensional constellations [1-5]. In particular, [1] proposed a four-dimensional, 64 symbol, equal energy constellation whose performance is compared with that of 64-HPSK in this paper.

Practical satellite communications systems use forward error correction coding techniques such as Reed Solomon Codes to improve bit error rates at low received energy levels due to the large distances between satellites and earth terminals. An increase in the Euclidean distance between the MHPSK symbol constellation points results in improved error performance as compared to traditional

modulation techniques such as M -ary phase-shift keying (MPSK) where symbol constellation points are defined on only two dimensions.

In satellite communications, due to the large distances between transmitters and receivers, received signal strength is often comparable to that of noise. The increasing need for more spectral efficiency on satellite uplinks that transmit video often compel the use of 16-PSK or 16-QAM. Unfortunately, 16-PSK suffers from high bit error rates at low energy per bit-to-noise power spectral density ratios E_b/N_0 . M -ary frequency shift-keying (MFSK) can be used to improve bit error performance, but the cost is a significant decrease in spectral efficiency. As a consequence of having unequal energy symbols, 16-QAM signals often must use significant amplifier back-off when used in satellite uplinks, and this does work given powerful enough amplifiers located at earth uplink stations. It should be noted that even 16-PSK with raised cosine pulse shaping requires some amplifier back-off but not as much as for 16-QAM because of the unequal energy symbols used in MQAM.

In this paper, a signal consisting of MHPSK modulation in combination with Reed Solomon (RS) coding to improve the probability of bit error for scenarios where the received signal energy is low is considered. Reed Solomon coding is used because the symbol order of this non-binary code can be matched to the modulation symbol order to improve the robustness of the communications link while minimizing the bandwidth expansion that results from the inclusion of error correction coding. In addition, 64-HPSK is compared to 8-PSK, 16-PSK, 16-QAM, and the four-dimensional, 64 signal constellation proposed in [1].

II. REED SOLOMON CODES WITH M -ARY HYPER PHASE SHIFT KEYING

The four orthonormal basis functions used to generate MHPSK are

$$\phi_1(t) = \frac{A}{\sqrt{E_s}} \cos(2\pi(f_c + 1/(2T))t) \quad (1)$$

$$\phi_2(t) = \frac{A}{\sqrt{E_s}} \sin(2\pi(f_c + 1/(2T))t) \quad (2)$$

$$\phi_3(t) = \frac{A}{\sqrt{E_s}} \sin(2\pi(f_c - 1/(2T))t) \quad (3)$$

$$\phi_4(t) = \frac{A}{\sqrt{E_s}} \cos(2\pi(f_c - 1/(2T))t) \quad (4)$$

where $E_s = A^2T/2$, the basis functions are defined for the symbol duration T , and $f_c = m/T$ where m is a positive integer.

A block diagram of an MHPSK system using Reed Solomon forward error correction coding is shown in Figure 1. The encoder takes k information symbols and produces n code symbols to be modulated and transmitted across the channel. With MPSK, the symbols are assigned to various phases around a circle in the two-dimensional signal space; however, with MHPSK the symbols are assigned to various phases in a four-dimensional signal space on the surface of a hyper-sphere. The $m = \log_2 M$ bits for each code symbol determine the symbol waveform according to

$$s_n(t) = \sqrt{E_s} [s_{n1}\phi_1(t) + s_{n2}\phi_2(t) + s_{n3}\phi_3(t) + s_{n4}\phi_4(t)] \quad (5)$$

where s_{n1} , s_{n2} , s_{n3} , and s_{n4} convey the coded information bits to be transmitted as described in Tables I and II for $M = 32$ and $M = 64$, respectively. The symbol mapping scheme for 16-HPSK consists of using the 16 vertices of a four-dimensional hypercube superimposed on the surface of a four-dimensional hyper-sphere. In Table I, $\sqrt{1/3}$ is approximated as 0.577, and in Table II, $\sqrt{2/3}$ is approximated as 0.817.

Figure 1: Block diagram of a modem with forward error control coding.

The 64-symbol constellation was determined by enforcing the following constraints. First, the 64 symbols are all equal energy and consist of one of two amplitude levels defined by

$$A^2 + 3B^2 = 1 \quad (6)$$

where $\pm A$ is used once and $\pm B$ is used three times for each symbol to get the required number of symbols in a

symmetrical constellation. Additionally, the number of nearest neighbors is minimized and the minimum squared-Euclidean distance between symbols is maximized by enforcing the relationship

$$d_{\min}^2 = \min \left[(2B)^2, 2(A - B)^2 \right] \quad (7)$$

where \min is the minimum of the two quantities. It should be noted that using the constraint of equal threshold distances

TABLE I: SYMBOL MAPPING VALUES FOR 32-HPSK

Bit Stream	Sn1	Sn2	Sn3	Sn4
00000	0.577	0.577	0.577	0
00001	0.577	0.577	0	0.577
00011	0.577	0	0.577	0.577
00010	0	0.577	0.577	0.577
00110	-0.577	0.577	0.577	0
00111	-0.577	0.577	0	-0.577
00101	-0.577	0	-0.577	-0.577
00100	0	0.577	-0.577	-0.577
01100	-0.577	0.577	-0.577	0
01101	-0.577	0.577	0	0.577
01111	-0.577	0	0.577	0.577
01110	0	-0.577	0.577	0.577
01010	0.577	-0.577	0.577	0
01011	0.577	-0.577	0	0.577
01001	0.577	0	-0.577	0.577
01000	0	-0.577	-0.577	0.577
11000	0.577	-0.577	-0.577	0
11001	0.577	-0.577	0	-0.577
11011	0.577	0	0.577	-0.577
11010	0	-0.577	0.577	-0.577
11110	-0.577	-0.577	0.577	0
11111	-0.577	-0.577	0	0.577
11101	-0.577	0	-0.577	0.577
11100	0	0.577	-0.577	0.577
10100	0.577	0.577	-0.577	0
10101	0.577	0.577	0	-0.577
10111	0.577	0	-0.577	-0.577
10110	0	-0.577	-0.577	-0.577
10010	-0.577	-0.577	-0.577	0
10011	-0.577	-0.577	0	-0.577
10001	-0.577	0	0.577	-0.577
10000	0	0.577	0.577	-0.577

between A and B and B and $-B$ provides a smaller minimum Euclidean distance than (7) does. The equal threshold distance constraint is used in [1], where a minimum squared-Euclidean distance $2E_b$ is achieved. Enforcing (6) and (7) to determine the constellation points for 64-HPSK, we obtain a minimum squared-Euclidean distance of $8E_b/3$.

A minimum Euclidean distance (MED) detector in the demodulator estimates the received code symbols based on the principle that the received signal is demodulated as the signal that is closest to one of the allowable M -ary signals. Therefore, the MED detector estimates the received code symbol as the symbol that is closest in the four-dimensional Euclidean space to one of the allowable M -ary symbols. This process is a form of maximum-likelihood detection that minimizes probability of received code symbol error [6]. The process then repeats itself for the next symbol in the data

stream and so on. These code symbol estimates form the input to the decoder. Finally, the decoder produces the estimated information bits [6-8].

With forward error correction coding, the probability of coded symbol error over the channel determines the probability of information bit error. The probability of channel, or code, symbol error are determined analytically using tight union bounds that are extremely accurate for probability of information bit errors on the order of 10^{-3} through 10^{-6} . Since this is the range of the values of interest for practical systems, the union bounds are useful for predicting performance as shown in Section III, where the union bound predicted performance accurately matches the performance obtained by Monte Carlo simulation.

The tight union bounds are obtained using a well known first order approximation for $M = 32$ and a second order approximation for $M = 64$ that are extremely accurate for probability of information bit error as shown in Section III [8]. The first order approximation is

$$p_s \cong N_n Q \left(\sqrt{\frac{d^2}{2N_o}} \right), \quad (8)$$

where d^2 is the minimum squared-Euclidean distance between the symbols and their nearest neighbors, and N_n is the number of nearest neighbors. The second order approximation simply adds another term to (8) that uses the minimum squared-Euclidean distance between the symbols and their second nearest neighbors.

For 16-HPSK, the minimum Euclidean distance between each of the symbols and their four nearest neighbors is $\sqrt{4E_c}$. Therefore, from (8) the channel symbol error probability for 16-HPSK can be approximated as

$$p_s \approx 4Q \left(\sqrt{\frac{2E_c}{N_o}} \right). \quad (9)$$

The exact channel symbol error probability for 16-HPSK can be found as

$$p_s = \left[1 - \left(1 - Q \left(\sqrt{\frac{\log_2(16)E_c}{2N_o}} \right) \right)^4 \right]. \quad (10)$$

Additionally, the coded energy per bit-to-noise PSD ratio is related to E_b/N_o by $E_c/N_o = r E_b/N_o$, where r is the code rate.

For 32-HPSK, the minimum Euclidean distance between each of the symbols and its six nearest neighbors is $\sqrt{10E_c/3}$. Therefore, from (8) the channel symbol error probability for 32-HPSK is

TABLE II: SYMBOL MAPPING VALUES FOR 64-HPSK

Bit Stream	Sn1	Sn2	Sn3	Sn4
000000	0.817	1/3	1/3	1/3
000001	0.817	1/3	1/3	-1/3
000011	0.817	1/3	-1/3	-1/3
000010	0.817	1/3	-1/3	1/3
000110	0.817	-1/3	-1/3	1/3
000111	0.817	-1/3	-1/3	-1/3
000101	0.817	-1/3	1/3	-1/3
000100	0.817	-1/3	1/3	1/3
001100	1/3	-0.817	1/3	1/3
001101	1/3	-0.817	1/3	-1/3
001111	1/3	-0.817	-1/3	-1/3
001110	1/3	-0.817	-1/3	1/3
001010	-1/3	-0.817	-1/3	1/3
001011	-1/3	-0.817	-1/3	-1/3
001001	-1/3	-0.817	1/3	-1/3
001000	-1/3	-0.817	1/3	1/3
011000	-0.817	-1/3	1/3	1/3
011001	-0.817	-1/3	1/3	-1/3
011011	-0.817	-1/3	-1/3	-1/3
011010	-0.817	-1/3	-1/3	1/3
011110	-0.817	1/3	-1/3	1/3
011111	-0.817	1/3	-1/3	-1/3
011101	-0.817	1/3	1/3	-1/3
011100	-0.817	1/3	1/3	1/3
010100	-1/3	1/3	0.817	1/3
010101	-1/3	1/3	0.817	-1/3
010111	-1/3	-1/3	0.817	-1/3
010110	-1/3	-1/3	0.817	1/3
010010	1/3	-1/3	0.817	1/3
010011	1/3	-1/3	0.817	-1/3
010001	1/3	1/3	0.817	-1/3
010000	1/3	1/3	0.817	1/3
110000	1/3	0.817	1/3	1/3
110001	1/3	0.817	1/3	-1/3
110011	1/3	0.817	-1/3	-1/3
110010	1/3	0.817	-1/3	1/3
110110	-1/3	0.817	-1/3	1/3
110111	-1/3	0.817	-1/3	-1/3
110101	-1/3	0.817	1/3	-1/3
110100	-1/3	0.817	1/3	1/3
111100	-1/3	1/3	1/3	0.817
111101	-1/3	1/3	-1/3	0.817
111111	-1/3	-1/3	-1/3	0.817
111110	-1/3	-1/3	1/3	0.817
111010	1/3	1/3	1/3	0.817
111011	1/3	-1/3	1/3	0.817
111001	1/3	-1/3	-1/3	0.817
111000	1/3	1/3	-1/3	0.817
101000	1/3	1/3	-0.817	1/3
101001	-1/3	1/3	-0.817	1/3
101011	-1/3	-1/3	-0.817	1/3
101010	1/3	-1/3	-0.817	1/3
101110	1/3	-1/3	-0.817	-1/3
101111	-1/3	-1/3	-0.817	-1/3
101101	-1/3	1/3	-0.817	-1/3
101100	1/3	1/3	-0.817	-1/3
100100	1/3	1/3	-1/3	-0.817
100101	1/3	-1/3	-1/3	-0.817
100111	1/3	-1/3	1/3	-0.817
100110	1/3	1/3	1/3	-0.817
100010	-1/3	1/3	1/3	-0.817
100011	-1/3	-1/3	1/3	-0.817
100001	-1/3	-1/3	-1/3	-0.817
100000	-1/3	1/3	-1/3	-0.817

$$p_s \approx 6Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{5E_c}{3N_0}}\right). \quad (11)$$

For 64-HPSK, each symbol has three nearest neighbors with a Euclidean distance of $\sqrt{8E_c/3}$ between each symbol. However, 64-HPSK symbols also have three additional symbols a Euclidean distance of $\sqrt{1681E_c/600}$ away. The reader can make an analogy between 64-HPSK and MQAM where there are four nearest neighbors and four more diagonal neighbors only slightly further away. Using error correction coding, the energy per coded bit is lower than the energy per information bit so that it is more likely for some of the symbol errors to jump to the second nearest set of neighbors. The channel symbol error probability for 64-HPSK is, therefore,

$$p_s \approx 3Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{4E_c}{3N_0}}\right) + 3Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{1681E_c}{1200N_0}}\right). \quad (12)$$

The decoded symbol error probability is [7]

$$P_s \approx \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n i \binom{n}{i} p_s^i (1-p_s)^{n-i} \quad (13)$$

where n is the number of coded symbols per block and t is the number of correctable symbols per block using Reed Solomon coding [7, 8]. The p_s term in (13) is taken from (10) through (12) depending on whether $M = 16$, $M = 32$, or $M = 64$, respectively. Since HPSK uses quasi-gray coding, the probability of bit error is very close to the lower bound

$$P_b \approx \frac{P_s}{m}, \quad (14)$$

where m is the number of bits per symbol [7, 8].

III. RESULTS

The performance of 8-PSK, 16-PSK, 16-QAM, 64-Welti, and MHPSK, all equal energy per symbol M -ary modulation techniques with the exception of 16-QAM, are compared by examining the probability of bit error versus E_b/N_0 when the information symbols are encoded using Reed Solomon codes. 16-PSK and 16-QAM are commonly used in many satellite uplinks that are concerned with spectral efficiency. The most useful comparison exists between 16-PSK, 16-QAM, 64-Welti, and 64-HPSK since they have the same spectral efficiency. The results in the figures referred to in this section are obtained using the equations in Section II. The simulation curves were achieved using a Monte Carlo simulation where each data point represents 1000 bit errors.

The results for 16-HPSK are shown in Figure 2. For 16-HPSK, the best coding gain is obtained using a (15, 9) RS code. However, the (15, 11) RS code that corresponds to an approximate code rate of 0.73 has almost the same probability of bit error as the (15, 9) RS code for P_b s of interest but with a lower bandwidth expansion. Notice that the simulation results lie very close to the lower bound.

The tremendous coding gain obtained using Reed Solomon coding with 32-HPSK is illustrated in Figure 3. The (31, 19) RS code offers the best coding gain, but the (31, 23) RS code, corresponding to a code rate of 0.74, has almost the same probability of bit error for P_b s of interest. Notice that the simulation results lie very close to the lower bound as before.

The vast coding gain improvement obtained using Reed Solomon coding for 64-HPSK is shown in Figure 4. The (63, 35) and (63, 39) RS codes all offer very good coding gains compared to uncoded 64-HPSK. The (63, 39) RS code offers the least bandwidth expansion of the two and corresponds to a code rate of 0.62. Additionally, the (63, 43) RS code, with an approximate code rate of 0.68, offers significant coding gain that is only slightly degraded as compared to the (63, 35) and (63, 39) RS codes. As the code rate increases above that for the (63, 43) RS code, performance begins to degrade as expected.

The performance obtained for 64-HPSK using Reed Solomon coding is significant because 16-PSK, 16-QAM, 64-

Figure 2: 16-HPSK performance with Reed Solomon coding.

Welti and 64-HPSK have the same spectral efficiency. Furthermore, many satellite systems use 16-PSK or 16-QAM for satellite uplinks concerned with spectral efficiency. Additionally, 64-HPSK with a (63, 43) code outperforms 8-PSK using the same (63, 43) code by 1.4 dB while having more spectral efficiency. Two 8-PSK symbols are encoded within each Reed Solomon coded symbol using a (63,43) code so the results refer to this as coded 8-PSK double symbols. The large coding gain improvements for 64-HPSK occur because HPSK takes advantage of four dimensions to increase the Euclidean distance between adjacent symbols. Reed Solomon coding is often used for M -ary modulations that can achieve high modulation orders such as MHPSK and MFSK [6-9]. Specifically, 64-HPSK takes advantage of a higher modulation order due to the previously mentioned ability to utilize four dimensions. MPSK is impractical for modulation orders larger than 16 because the symbols begin to crowd together as M increases. The performance of 64-HPSK, 8-PSK, 16-PSK, 16-QAM, and the 64-Welti constellation using

the four basis functions (1) through (4), all encoded with Reed Solomon codes, is compared in Figure 5. The 64-Weltri constellation is taken from [1] and refers to a proposed four-dimensional signal space constellation.

Figure 3: 32-HPSK performance with Reed Solomon coding.

Figure 4: 64-HPSK performance with Reed Solomon coding.

For 64-HPSK a probability of bit error of 10^{-5} is achieved with an E_b/N_0 of 7.8 dB using a (63, 43) RS code. Using the same (63, 43) RS code, 8-PSK has a probability of bit error of 10^{-5} with an E_b/N_0 of 9.2 dB. This represents a 1.4 dB gain for 64-HPSK compared to 8-PSK using the same Reed Solomon code. The 64-Weltri constellation does outperform 8-PSK due to the increased Euclidean distance between symbols but performs 0.4 dB worse than 64-HPSK at a probability of bit error of 10^{-5} . 64-HPSK offers performance at slightly more than half the required energy of 16-QAM at a comparable spectral efficiency. The comparison between MPSK, 16-QAM, the 64-Weltri constellation, and MHPK is further

highlighted in Table III, which shows null-to-null bandwidths using rectangular pulse shaping to match the literature [6, 8].

Figure 5: Comparison of 64-HPSK, 8-PSK, 16-PSK, 16-QAM, and 64-Weltri with Reed Solomon coding.

TABLE III: COMPARISON OF MODULATION TYPES

Modulation	Code Rate	E_b / N_0 at $P_b = 10^{-5}$	Spectral Efficiency _{n-n}
8-PSK	0.68	9.2 dB	1.02
16-PSK	0.68	13.8 dB	1.36
16-QAM	0.68	10.1 dB	1.36
64-HPSK	0.68	7.8 dB	1.36
64-Weltri	0.68	8.2 dB	1.36
16-HPSK	0.73	7.6 dB	0.97
32-HPSK	0.74	7.8 dB	1.23

IV. SUMMARY

MHPK is an ideal modulation technique for energy limited applications such as satellite communications uplinks concerned with spectral efficiency. This is because the signal is often received with very low signal power due to the large distances between communication satellites and earth stations. As a result of the low received signal strength, error correction coding is often used in the satellite communications waveform.

64-HPSK, which has the same spectral efficiency as 16-PSK and 16-QAM, achieves superior probability of bit error performance using Reed Solomon coding. The 6 dB and 2.3 dB improvements in E_b/N_0 for 64-HPSK over 16-PSK and 16-QAM, respectively, using Reed Solomon codes illustrate its superior performance at a probability of bit error of 10^{-5} . 64-HPSK utilizes four dimensions to increase the Euclidean distance between adjacent symbols. Due to the increased Euclidean distance between the MHPK symbols, MHPK performs better with Reed Solomon coding than either 16-PSK or 16-QAM. This same trend with regards to improved performance obtained using four dimensions is also observed for the 64-Weltri constellation. Note that 64-HPSK performs better than the 64-Weltri constellation due to

increased Euclidean distance between the *MHPSK* symbols. The best code rates for HPSK from the results presented in this paper vary from approximately 0.6 to 0.74.

Future work will compare *MHPSK* to 16-PSK and 16-QAM combined with high code rate low density parity check (LDPC) codes that have higher spectral efficiencies than can be obtained using trellis coded modulation with 16-PSK or 16-QAM. Currently, LDPC codes use block lengths of 64,800 bits to achieve excellent coding gains at high code rates. To enable a fair comparison in terms of long block lengths, a Reed Solomon encoder will encode two *MHPSK* symbols at a time just as was done in this paper with 8-PSK. Additional future work will compare *MHPSK* with two subcarrier orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing using either 8-PSK or 8-QAM modulation on the subcarriers and incorporating peak-to-average power ratio effects.

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